

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE GREAT SILK ROAD IN THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF THE TURKIC STATES

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Abstract. *This article explained the role of the Great Silk Road in the development of the Turkic states. An overview of how important it served the ancient and present Turkic states is given. Feedback has been provided on how the Great Silk Road economically fulfilled the dominant vase for the history and development of all states in its direction.*

Keywords: *civilization, Great Silk Road, globalization, trade, economic development, economic trajectories.*

Introduction. One of the outstanding achievements of ancient civilizations is considered the Great Silk Road. It served for the first time in human history as a system linking different countries and peoples in the vast expanses from the Mediterranean to the Pacific, linking their, economic political and spiritual culture (1-picture). [1]

The concept of the “Great Silk Road” was used in the period to introduce two different objects: the West and the East, and to relate to valuable goods –silk [2]. For the first time, the term was used by the German scientist Ferdinand Richthofen in his classic scientific work “China” in 1877. Thus, it sheds light on the Great Silk Road, a road that connects various parts of the vast Eurasian continent. Since the first decade of the 21st century, the “establishment of borders” and trends have begun to be emphasized by kata.

The participation of the countries of Central Asia and the Far East in the process of globalization has become increasingly intense. Now the well-being of the whole world in the economic, social and political spheres has become dependent on the participation of the Great Silk Road. The most important area of the Great Silk Road is not only the dissemination of information, but also its exchange. Thus, cultural upheavals began to spread information among peoples through trade caravans. All these processes led to cultural adaptation, the emergence of new “foreign culture” phenomena and actions, the impetus for the formation of a new worldview. Of the caravan routes, that is, the parts of India adjacent to the Great Silk Road-China, China-Central Asia, the middle and Middle East, the Mediterranean countries of Asia-an important historical roller plays in this. From this we can conclude that the Duke Silk Road did an effective intermediary roll as an exchange of cultural political and economic resources across the country without a military march and forced threats.[3]

The Great Silk Road is a trade route that in ancient times divided the East with the West, a phenomenon characteristic of the history of human development, its desire to unite and exchange with cultural values, to achieve markets for the sale of vital space and products. These roads were important before the sea, ocean roads were opened.

1-picture. Great Silk Road

The Great Silk Road and the Economic Development of Turkic States

The Great Silk Road, an ancient network of trade routes, played a pivotal role in shaping the economic landscapes of many regions, including the Turkic states. Spanning from China to the Mediterranean, this historical corridor facilitated not only the exchange of goods but also the transfer of culture, technology, and ideas. For the Turkic states, which include modern-day countries such as Turkey, Azerbaijan, and Kazakhstan, the Silk Road was instrumental in their economic development [4]. These states served as crucial intermediaries between East and West, leveraging their strategic positions to control and benefit from the trade routes.

Trade along the Silk Road brought substantial economic advantages. Silk, spices, precious metals, and other valuable commodities flowed through these regions, generating revenue and fostering economic growth. The Turkic states acted as vital hubs in this trade network, enhancing their infrastructure and markets. This influx of goods and wealth catalyzed local industries and urban development, laying the foundation for prosperous civilizations. [5]

Moreover, the Silk Road facilitated cultural and technological exchanges that further boosted economic progress. Turkic states adopted and adapted innovations in agriculture, navigation, and manufacturing, which improved productivity and efficiency. The sharing of knowledge and skills also promoted cross-cultural collaborations, which enriched the social and economic fabric of the region.

In summary, the Great Silk Road was more than a series of trade routes; it was a lifeline that connected diverse economies and cultures. For the Turkic states, its influence extended beyond trade, contributing significantly to their economic development and historical legacy. The enduring impact of this ancient network underscores the importance of historical trade routes in shaping the economic trajectories of nations.

The economic importance of the Great Silk Road lay in its ability to connect different markets and cultures. Goods such as silk, spices, precious metals and fabrics, which were in demand in different parts of the world, moved through these trade routes. Turkmen, Kazakh

and other Turkic states located at the crossroads of these routes have the opportunity to benefit significantly from the transit of goods. The Great Silk Road has become an important economic incentive for the Turkic states. These States served as key transit hubs, which contributed to their economic prosperity. With the increase in trade, the need for infrastructure development, urban construction and technology improvement has increased. Economic growth has contributed to the development of local markets and industries.

In addition, the Silk Road has become a channel for the transmission of cultural and technological innovations. The Turkic states borrowed and adapted new technologies in the field of agriculture, navigation and production, which contributed to increased efficiency and productivity. [6]

As a result, the Great Silk Road not only promoted economic exchange, but also had a significant impact on the development of civilizations, paving the way for economic and cultural prosperity. This historic route has become an important element of the global economy and has left a lasting legacy in the economic development of the countries through which it passed.

Conclusion. In general, the Great Silk Road was of great importance to the ancient and present-day Turkic states. It was he who greatly helped them in all areas, in particular, their economic development. It served as a bridge in their establishment of economic, political, social relations with other states. The development of impoverished states through the Great Silk Road was eased. Developed nations have made many contributions to the development of the trade sector.

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